

CHEMICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL BASES OF AMMONIUM NITRATE PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT *the article describes a chemical and technological scheme for the production of ammonium nitrate, a diagram of material flows of production is constructed, with the help of which the share of production waste for each stage was determined.*

Keywords: *ammonium nitrate, Sankey diagram, material balance, production technology.*

The chemical and technological scheme for the production of ammonium nitrate is complex and includes several stages (Figures 1, 2). The first stage is to obtain a solution of magnesium nitrate (magnesia additive) [1]. To improve the physico-chemical properties of the product, a solution of magnesium nitrate with a mass fraction of 35% obtained from magnesite (MgCO_3) is introduced into the solution before its evaporation:

As a result of the reaction, heat is released, which is used in the process line. Preparation of a magnesia additive is carried out in a batch reactor P-1 as a result of the interaction of caustic magnesite, juice vapor condensate and weak nitric acid.

The interaction of magnesite with nitric acid ($\omega = 36\%$) is carried out for 4 hours at atmospheric pressure at a temperature of no more than 80°C until the

complete decomposition of the magnesite. The mass concentration of Mg is brought to 120-140 g/dm³, and nitric acid to 25-50 g/dm³ [2]. After filtration, the purified magnesia additive enters the E-1 storage, and then into the heat of neutralization utilization apparatus (ITN) P-3 and the doneutralizer P-4 [3].

At the second stage, nitric acid is neutralized with gaseous ammonia to obtain a solution of ammonium nitrate (Fig. 2).

The process is carried out at atmospheric pressure in two parallel operating devices ITN P-3_{1,2} at a temperature of 148-165 ° C. The output is a solution of AC with a mass fraction of amselitra $\geq 89\%$. During the neutralization process, heat is released, which is used to concentrate the resulting AC solution.

Complete neutralization proceeds at high speed in the reaction zone of the lower part of the apparatus, and then the solution is removed from the apparatus [3]. Nitric acid is heated to a temperature of 75-80 ° C in the T-2 heater before being fed to the reactors. The same thing happens with ammonia gas in T-1 devices, where it is heated to 120-180 ° C.

Acidic environment is maintained in ITN devices. Upon evaporation of the ammonium nitrate solution, juice vapor is formed, 20-40% of which is used as a coolant in T-2 nitric acid heaters, the rest is sent to the X-29 scrubber. The temperatures of juice vapor and ammonium nitrate in the reaction zone are the same [4].

Fig. 1. Chemical scheme of preparation of raw materials and production of ammonium nitrate

The juice vapor enters the separation part a of the product, where an acidified weak solution of ammonium nitrate ($\omega(HNO_3) \approx 20 \text{ g/dm}^3$) is supplied from the tank E-20 [5], then the solution enters the reaction part of the ITN apparatus, where it is mixed with the reaction solution. Upon contact of NH_4NO_3 with an acidified solution, non-reacted NH_3 is absorbed from it.

The NH_4NO_3 solution from the ITN devices enters the P-4 doneutralizer, in which the excess HNO_3 is neutralized by gaseous NH_3 . To maintain the alkaline environment of the solution, a magnesia additive is introduced into the solution from the E-1 storage before being fed to the evaporation stage [2].

Fig. 2. Technological scheme of ammonium nitrate production

The control doneutralizer R-97 before the evaporation apparatus T-10 eliminates the ingress of unreacted ammonia at the evaporation stage.

The juice vapor from the doneutralizers is sent to capture ammonia in the X-86 neutralizer. The mass fraction of the spent NH_4NO_3 solution sent to the X-98 steam-air mixture washer does not exceed 30%, and the mass concentration of HNO_3 is 20 g/dm^3 . The purified juice steam from the X-86 scrubber is sent to the X-29_{1,2} scrubber.

After reaching the mass fraction of ammonium nitrate in a solution of at least 89%, the solution from the doneutralizer P-97 is sent to the evaporation apparatus T-10.

At the third stage, the resulting amselitre solution is evaporated to obtain a highly concentrated melt, and then the melt is pumped into a granulation tower. The mass fraction in the solution of ammonium nitrate is brought to 99.7%. Evaporation

of the salt solution is carried out at atmospheric pressure due to the use of condensation heat in the evaporation apparatus T-10.

Atmospheric air is supplied to the heater T-11, which is heated to 175-190 °C with saturated steam. The mass concentration of NH_4NO_3 is not more than 8 g/m^3 and NH_3 is not more than 2 g/m^3 [6]. The resulting mixture enters the X-98 washer, where it is washed with an acidified NH_4NO_3 solution coming from the X-86 scrubber [3].

Then the steam-air mixture with a mass concentration of NH_4NO_3 not exceeding 0.2 g/m^3 not exceeding 0.3 g/m^3 is washed and mixed with juice steam from ITN devices and sent to the X-29 scrubber.

After the X-98 washer, a 35% ammonium nitrate solution is sent to the E-20 tank. Before pumping to the granulation stage, ammonium nitrate surfactants ($t = 175\text{-}185 \text{ }^\circ \text{C}$) are alkalized with ammonia from the evaporation apparatus in the P-13 deionizer. The ammonium nitrate melt from the P-13 hydraulic seal enters the E-15 tank, from where it is fed into the granulation tower, into the pressure tank E-23 [3].

The last stage of NH_4NO_3 production is the granulation of a highly concentrated ammonium nitrate melt in a metal granulating tower, the height of the granules falling is 50 m.

The minimum mass fraction of AU in the melt is 99.7%, and the temperature is $175\text{-}185 \text{ }^\circ \text{C}$. From the pressure tank E-23, the saltpeter float enters the risers in front of the granulators, where it is evenly sprayed in the form of droplets through the X-26 pelletizers over the entire cross section of the full volume of the tower. The oncoming air flow rising at a speed of $1.0\text{-}1.8 \text{ m/s}$ is created by the V-28 fans. The falling droplets are cooled and crystallized in the form of pellets. The obtained NH_4NO_3 granules with a temperature of $70\text{-}120 \text{ }^\circ \text{C}$ fall on the cone of the granulation tower and enter the PT-30 conveyor through the discharge holes.

The PT-30 conveyor feeds ammonium nitrate granules to the grate of the pellet cooling apparatus in the fluidized bed X-33. In the case of saltpeter sticking

on the cones and walls of the granite tower, lumps and large particles may form on the grid. Large fractions are dissolved in tank E 31, into which a weak NH_4NO_3 solution is fed, which enters the drainage tank E-6. From the X-33 apparatus, dry exhaust air enters the granite tower and is then sent to the X-29 scrubber for cleaning.

The control of the main stages of the process is carried out on the central control panel (CPU). The control system is remote, so the human factor plays an important role. The subsequent regulation of the process parameters is carried out using electrical systems [4]. The safety system at work plays a dominant role. The occurrence of emergency situations on the production line is prevented by a system of locks and protections. In addition, at each stage of the process there is equipment that controls temperature, pressure, volumes of reacting components, acidity of the medium, etc. All personnel of the enterprise are instructed on safety at work.

After cooling in the X-33 fluidized bed apparatus, the resulting AC is fed to conveyors for packaging and shipment in bags or in bulk to road or rail transport. The whole process of packing and loading is mechanized. Control and alarm of failures is carried out by the central control panel of the department of instrumentation and automation (CPU Instrumentation and Control System).

Fig. 3. Analysis of material flows of ammonium nitrate production. Sankey Diagram

Packaging of ammonium nitrate in bags is carried out using semi-automatic packaging machines. Dispensers of these devices weigh portions of ammonium nitrate by 50 kg, fill them into bags, and after filling, the packaged finished product is loaded into a conveyor belt into road or rail transport.

To assess the economic efficiency of technological processes, the equations of material and energy (thermal) balances are used [7].

The material balance is made on the basis of stoichiometry. The balance consists of "arrival" – the total mass of substances entering production, and "consumption" - the total mass of materials leaving production. When drawing up a balance, discrepancies between income and expenditure of 23% are considered acceptable. If the discrepancies exceed 5%, then it is necessary to look for the reasons for the discrepancy: losses, purity of raw materials and products, instrument readings, errors in the calculation method, etc. The material balance is the basis of any technological calculation, in addition, it is a production control tool [8].

Based on the material balance of production, the percentage ratio of resources used at each stage of production was calculated and a Sankey diagram was constructed to visually represent the dynamics of material flows (Fig.3). The width of the flows is proportional to the amount of resources consumed at each stage.

Thus, the analysis of material flows based on the Sankey diagram allowed us to determine the production waste, which is 0.5% at the neutralization stage, 0.03% at the pre-neutralization stage, 0.03% at the granulation stage of ammonium nitrate.

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